

Assessing Holistic Health: Exploring Bio-Well GDV as a Comprehensive Measurement Tool

¹Smita Verma, ²Dr. Manini Srivastava

¹Research Scholar, ²Assistant Professor
Department of Psychology
Lucknow University, 226007

Abstract- This study investigates the utility of the Bio-Well Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV) as a comprehensive measurement tool for assessing holistic health. As society embraces a more holistic approach to well-being, there is a growing need for versatile assessment tools that consider the interconnectedness of physical, mental, and emotional health. Bio-Well GDV is based on the principles of electro-photonics which offer a non-invasive means to capture and analyse the human energy field and also provide insights into the subtle energies that influence our overall health. Through an extensive review of existing research, this presentation explores the potential of Bio-Well GDV to assess various facets of holistic health, including stress levels, energy balance, and emotional well-being. This presentation highlights its promising role in advancing our understanding of holistic health and the potential integration of complementary healing modalities into mainstream healthcare practices.

Keywords: Bio-Well GDV camera, holistic health, electro-photonics, energy field, well-being assessment, holistic health.

Introduction:

Holistic health is a comprehensive approach to well-being, that recognizes the interconnectedness of various aspects of an individual's life. Rather than focusing solely on physical health, it emphasizes the integration of physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual health to achieve overall well-being. This approach is increasingly recognized as essential for addressing the complexities of human health and promoting a more balanced and fulfilling life.

The significance of holistic health lies in its recognition of the multifaceted nature of human wellness. By acknowledging the intricate interplay between physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual factors, it offers a more comprehensive framework for understanding and promoting health. This approach encourages individuals to actively participate in their well-being, empowering them to make informed decisions that promote balance and harmony in all aspects of life. Holistic health also promotes the prevention of illness and the maintenance of health, focusing not only on the absence of disease but also on the enhancement of vitality and quality of life. By considering the whole person, rather than just isolated symptoms or conditions, holistic health facilitates a deeper understanding of the individual's unique health needs and fosters a more personalized and effective approach to healthcare.

This research study is all about exploring how useful Bio-Well GDV can be for understanding our overall health better. It's like trying to connect the dots between our physical and emotional well-being. It could even help us bring together different ways of staying healthy, like natural healing methods, with the usual healthcare we get from doctors.

Gas Discharge Visualization Technology:

Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV) is a unique method that integrates both Eastern and Western principles of medicine to assess the electrical activity of the human body. Our bodies emit natural electrophotonic waves in general, but the intensity of these waves changes during illness and this affects electron communication. GDV captures these electrophotonic emissions which create GDV-grams, enabling real-time assessment of an individual's functional state. This biometric technique extracts stimulated electrons and photons from the skin's surface using pulsed electromagnetic fields, this process is called "photoelectron emission."

The core of GDV relies on "sliding gas discharge," where short voltage pulses stimulate electrophotonic emissions by exciting molecules in the surrounding hydrogen, resulting in a glow measured by GDV. The data collected helps unveil electro-photon processes underlying the body's function.

Biometric GDV method is a non-invasive method which makes it entirely safe, it uses microamp-level pulse current that do not induce tissue depolarization or physiological changes. It allows measurements under normal conditions, without special preparation or lighting adjustments.

The GDV process involves two phases: one without a filter and another with a filter. Initially, electrons from the outer skin layers and surrounding tissue are extracted, followed by electrons from deeper tissues. These electrons are sourced

from various molecular systems, forming an "electron cloud" that occupies a specific spatial area. Quantum mechanics principles make pinpointing an electron's precise location within this cloud impossible.

The energy measurement technique known as response to stimulus involves the application of a weak electrical current to the fingertip of a subject for a duration of less than a millisecond. This leads to a specific physiological and psychological reaction within the human body, and each individual demonstrates a unique response to this stimulus, resulting in varying output. During this process, the fingertip emits electrons, which collide with and excite air molecules, subsequently generating a visible glow.

This glow is then recorded using a video camera, and the resulting digital image of the glow is further analyzed using specialized software. The software utilizes standard graphs for evaluation, ultimately allowing for the measurement of energy based on the analysis of these digital images. (Jhonson, R.D. et al. ,2002)

Steps involved in Gas Discharge Visualization Technology:

- 1. Photon and Electron Emission:** Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV) begins with the application of a small electric pulse to the subject, which stimulates the emission of photons and primary electrons from the subject's surface. This phenomenon is known as "photo-electron emissions."
- 2. Glow Creation:** The emitted photons and electrons excite the molecules on the subject's surface, creating a visible glow or energy field. This radiant energy field is captured by a GDV camera.
- 3. Electro-Photonic Imaging:** GDV is also referred to as "electro-photonic imaging" because it involves capturing and visualizing the electro-photonic emissions produced by the subject's surface when stimulated by the electric pulse.
- 4. Electric Field Generation:** The intense emission of gas, triggered by the voltage pulse and electronic photonic emission, creates an electric field surrounding the subject. This electric field represents the energy field of the subject's surface.
- 5. Diagnostic Analysis:** The GDV technique which is based on the principle of Kirlian photography, captures these energy field images. These images are then studied for the assessment of the health parameters of the subject. Variations in these parameters are noted and analyzed.

Method:

A thorough examination of academic literature was performed, covering the timeframe from 1990 to 2023. The primary search terms utilized were "gas discharge visualization," accompanied by related terms such as "holistic health," "psychology," "alternative medicine," "prevention," "diagnosis," "treatment," "acupuncture," "yoga," and "homeopathy." This comprehensive search aimed to gather relevant scholarly articles and publications related to the specified keywords.

Discussion:

The integration of computerized biometric tools into the field of medicine holds great promise for advancing disease identification and improving individualized medical care. Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV) stands out as a potential vehicle to meet the current demands of medical biometrics by enabling the early identification of diseases and characterizing the functional state of organs and organ systems under various conditions. Here are detailed points explaining the potential of GDV in medical biometrics and the role of computer science:

- 1. Disease Identification:** Medical biometrics focuses on identifying diseases through unique biological signatures. GDV offers a non-invasive way to measure electro-photonic emissions from the body. Diseases often lead to changes in the body's electrical activity, resulting in an increase in entropy and deviation from the normal functional state. GDV can capture these deviations and provide data for disease identification.
- 2. Translational Perspective:** The involvement of computer science brings a translational perspective to medical biometrics. Computer scientists can collaborate with medical professionals to develop and apply computational tools and models that enhance disease identification and analysis using GDV data.
- 3. Quantitative Analysis:** Computer modeling tools can be used to quantify the intensity of electro-photonic emission in specific sectors of the GDV diagram. This quantitative analysis allows for a more precise assessment of deviations from the norm, aiding in disease detection and monitoring the health status in detail during and after the treatment.
- 4. Integration with Diagnosis:** Computer science can facilitate the integration of GDV data with existing diagnostic methods. By correlating GDV findings with established medical diagnoses, healthcare practitioners can gain a deeper understanding of disease patterns and enhance the accuracy of disease identification.
- 5. Biometric Disease Identification:** GDV can be used in combination with computer modeling for early detection of disease. This means that unique electro-photonic signatures associated with specific diseases can be identified, allowing for early and accurate disease detection without invasive procedures which will prevent the individual from various health issues that too even before the onset of the symptoms.

6. Personalized Medicine: The use of GDV and computerized biometrics can contribute to personalized medicine by tailoring treatments based on an individual's specific disease profile and functional state. This can lead to more effective and targeted medical interventions.

7. Comprehensive and Cost-Effective Pathology Monitoring Tool: In routine modern medicine, minimizing costs while effectively monitoring complex pathologies remains a challenge. Our Findings: GDV as an All-in-One Monitoring Solution. According to research, employing Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV) presents a practical and economical approach to simultaneously track all bodily organs and subsystems. Confirmatory lab tests are necessary only to validate GDV Screening and Diagram data.

The diagram here is a sample of the energy levels of various regions show by the Bio-well GDV camera:

Image source: Understanding the effectiveness of a therapy using GDV Bio-Well Camera. (n.d.). <https://wellness-space.net/effectiveness-of-the-therapy-gdv-bio-well-camera/>. https://wellness-space.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Compare-diagram-2016-07-24-15_15-S-2.jpg

Table representing some case studies and the effect of the given therapy designed for each individual on the basis of the GDV energy diagram:

Case	Condition	Affected Areas Revealed by Initial GDV Camera	Symptoms	Treatment Process	Follow-up
1	Fatigue, general wellness	Overall weakness, low vitality.	Chronic tiredness, irregular exercise	Slow deep breathing of 3 rounds of 20 breaths each	Reduced fatigue, better sleep, improved sense of well-being
2	Diabetes, Weight Loss	Pancreas (lowest C), stable Pituitary C	Chronic diabetes, weight gain, knee pain	15 minutes of Kapaalabhaati twice a day	Significant weight loss, insulin discontinued
3	Insomnia, Weight Management	Nervous system (lowest C), increased Pituitary E	Severe insomnia, overweight	6 restrictive throat breaths for vagal stimulation, thrice daily	Improved sleep, enhanced wellness, no weight loss, increased Pituitary C with reduced coherence
4	Plantar Fasciitis	Nervous system (lowest C)	Sensations, sleep disturbance	Nervous System Stimulation	Sensations disappeared, improved nervous system and spine communication, relieved from pain and discomfort.

Case	Condition	Affected Areas Revealed by GDV Camera	Initial Symptoms	Treatment Process	Follow-up
5	Persistent Headache	Spinal Alignment	Increasing daytime headache	Gentle spinal alignment through yoga	Pain reduced to 0, improved nervous system and spine communication
6	Vitiligo	Liver Activation	Increasing vitiligo	Yoga exercises for abdominal area massage	Subsided vitiligo activation, improved liver energy

The study of articles on alternative medicine indicates that GDV is primarily employed in the practices of homeopathy, yoga, and acupuncture. This method serves not only as a means of diagnosing and evaluating the overall health condition but also as a tool to facilitate appropriate acupuncture, homeopathic, or yoga treatments. Moreover, GDV serves as a valuable device for tracking the progress and effectiveness of various treatment plans.

Conclusion:

By harnessing the power of electro-photonic emissions and advanced computational tools, it becomes possible to detect diseases at early stages, provide individualized care, and enhance our understanding of human health and physiology. This interdisciplinary approach holds great promise for the future of medicine. This can be summarised in the below points:

- Integration of Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV) and computer science has the potential to revolutionize disease identification and healthcare practices.
- GDV technology captures and analyzes electro-photonic emissions, providing valuable insights into the physiological state of individuals.
- Early disease detection before visible symptoms can improve patient outcomes through prompt and personalized treatment plans.
- Comprehensive GDV data contributes to a better understanding of individual health profiles, leading to tailored healthcare solutions.
- The integration facilitates real-time data analysis, enabling healthcare professionals to monitor treatment efficacy and disease progression.
- Collaboration between medical professionals, data scientists, and technologists fosters innovation and the development of advanced algorithms and predictive models.
- This interdisciplinary approach has the potential to transform modern medicine, offering improved health outcomes and a better quality of life for individuals worldwide.

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